

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Srinivas Nagar, Mukka- 574 146, Mangalore.

(Private University Established by Karnataka Govt. ACT No.42 of 2013, Recognized by UGC, New Delhi, & Member of Association of Indian Universities, New Delhi)

To,

Sub: To participate in BOS meeting of CSSH.

Greetings from College of Social Sciences and Humanities!

We would like to request you to participate in our Board of Studies meeting which will be conducted on **26th June 2017** at 1.00 P.M. to discuss the academic matters at room no 6, at College of Social Sciences, Srinivas University. Kindly find the attached agenda below.

Agenda

1. To plan the syllabus
2. To offer dual specialization subject
3. Internship
4. Field Practicum
5. Study material preparation
6. Academic calendar and exams
7. Internal assessment
8. Attendance
9. SAAS
10. Question paper patters
11. Internal and External Paper setters
12. Valuation
13. Any other matter

Your participation will be highly appreciable.

Thanking you.

Yours Sincerely,

Dr. Laveena D'Mello

Dean, College of Social Sciences and Humanities,
Srinivas University, City Campus,
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru- 575001.

Date: 16th June 2017

Place: Mangaluru.

DEAN
College of Social Science & Humanities
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

Attachment: Subject copy of MSW course

CC to;

1. Dr. Suresh Kumar P.M., Professor, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru- 575001.
2. Dr. I.C. Licamma, Professor, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru- 575001.
3. Prof. Pradeep M.D., Assistant Professor, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru- 575001.
4. Mrs. Indu Nair, Part time faculty, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru- 575001.
5. Mr. Gururaj Ganapathi Gowda, Research Scholar, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru- 575001.
6. Dr. Meena Montheiro, Dean, Research Council, School of Social Work, Roshni Nilaya, Mangaluru- 575001.

Ravi
DEAN
College of Social Science & Humanities
Srinivas University
Mangaluru-575001

Srinivas University

College of Social Science and Humanities

The Board of Studies meeting was conducted at Srinivas University City Conference room on 26th June 2017 at 1.00 P.M. to discuss the academic matters.

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The following members were present for the meeting

1. Dr. Suresh Kumar P.M.
2. Dr. I.C. Liciamma
3. Mr. Pradeep M.D.
4. Mrs. Laveena D'Mello
5. Mrs. Indu Nair
6. Dr. Meena Monthiero

During the BOS meeting, the following aspects were discussed and the resolutions were taken.

1. **To plan the syllabus:** The syllabus copy was given in advance to refer and same was discussed. Some changes were done in the syllabus and same was approved.
Resolution: The syllabus was approved by the BOS members.

Attachment:**COURSE STRUCTURE – DUAL SPECIALIZATION****HUMAN RESOURCES DEVELOPMENT AND MEDICAL AND PSYCHIATRIC SOCIAL WORK**

SEMETER 1	SEMESTER 2
Written papers 4 x 100 marks 1. Social Work - History and Philosophy 2. Social Case work 3. Social Group work 4. Organizational Psychology	Written papers 4 x 100 marks 1. Indian Society – Polity & Economy 2. Community Organization & Social Action 3. Social Welfare Administration 4. Social Research & Statistics
Fundamentals of Computer & Information Technology – 50 marks	Fundamentals of Computer & Information Technology – 50 marks
Field practicum – 100 marks (2 days in a week – Friday, Saturday)	Field practicum – 100 marks (2 days in a week – Friday, Saturday)
Communications Skills and Language Proficiency – 50 marks	Communication Skills and Language Proficiency – 50 marks
Seminar and Group presentation – 50 marks	Seminar and Group presentation – 50 marks
Total - 650 marks	Total - 650 marks
SEMETER 3	SEMESTER 4
Written papers 4 x 100 marks 1. Personnel Management & Human Resource Development 2. Medical Social Work 3. Management Concepts 4. Working with Children and Adolescence	Written papers 4 x 100 marks 1. Labour Laws 2. Industrial Relations and Labour Welfare 3. Psychiatric Social Work 4. Therapeutic Counselling
Field practicum – 100 marks (2 days in a week – Monday, Tuesday)	Field practicum – 100 marks (2 days in a week – Monday, Tuesday)
Summer Placement – 100 marks	Research Project – 100 marks (External Viva)
Seminar and Group presentation – 50 marks	Placement Training – 25 marks Case Study on the Research Topic – 25 marks
Total - 650 marks	Total - 650 marks

COURSE STRUCTURE

SEMETER 1. Written papers 4 x 100 marks				
Sl. No.	Name of the Paper	Total Marks	Hours of Teaching/week	Credits
1	Social Work - History and Philosophy	100	4	4
2	Social Case work	100	4	4
3	Social Group work	100	4	4
4	Organizational Psychology	100	4	4
5	Fundamentals of Computer & Information Technology	50	2	2
6	Field practicum (2 days in a week – Friday, Saturday)	100	16	12
7	Communication Skills and Language Proficiency	50	2	2
8	Seminar and Group presentation	50	2	2
Total		650	38	34

SEMESTER 2. Written papers 4 x 100 marks				
Sl. No.	Name of the Paper	Total Marks	Hours of Teaching/week	Credits
1	Indian Society – Polity & Economy	100	4	4
2	Community Organization & Social Action	100	4	4
3	Social Welfare Administration	100	4	4
4	Social Research & Statistics	100	4	4
5	Fundamentals of Computer & Information Technology	50	2	2
6	Field practicum (2 days in a week – Friday, Saturday)	100	16	12
7	Communication Skills and Language Proficiency	50	2	2
8	Seminar and Group presentation – 50 marks	50	2	2
Total - 650 marks		650	38	34

**HUMAN RESOURCES DEVELOPMENT AND PSYCHIATRIC SOCIAL WORK
DUAL SPECIALIZATION**

SEMETER 3. Written papers 4 x 100 marks				
Sl. No.	Name of the Paper	Total Marks	Hrs of Teaching/ week	Credits
1	Personnel Management & HRD	100	4	4
2	Medical Social Work	100	4	4
3	Management Concepts	100	4	4
4	Working with Children and Adolescence	100	4	4
5	Field practicum (2 days in a week – Monday, Tuesday)	100	16	12
6	Summer Placement	100	4	4
7	Seminar and Group presentation	50	2	2
Total - 650 marks		650	38	34

SEMESTER 4. Written papers 4 x 100 marks				
Sl. No.	Name of the Paper	Total Marks	Hours of Teaching/week	Credits
1.	Industrial Relations & Labour Welfare	100	4	4
2.	Psychiatric Social Work	100	4	4
3.	Labour Laws	100	4	4
4.	Therapeutic counselling	100	4	4
5	Field practicum (2 days in a week – Monday, Tuesday)	100	16	12
6	Research Project (External Viva)	100	4	4
7	Placement Training, Case Study on the Research Topic	50	2	2
Total		650	38	34

Examination Pattern :Theory Papers : Internal Assessment Marks :

Internal Assessment Marks are based on Assignments, & Internal Exams.

S. No.	Assessment Method	Marks
1	Assignments	10
2	Internal Exams (I & II)	40
Total		50

Semester Exam Marks :

At the end of each semester, examinations will be conducted for all the papers to be covered in that semester and evaluation will be done for 50 marks each. The timings of the examination will be followed as per academic calendar.

Pattern of Question Paper in End Semester Examination for Fourth semester

The question paper pattern in each Semester Exam for 50 marks consists of Two marks questions 6 questions out of 8 (12 marks), Seven marks questions 4 out of 6 questions (28 marks) , and one long essay of 10 marks out of two (10 marks).

No. of Questions	Type	Marks/Question	Total Marks
6 out of 8	Short answers	$6 \times 2 = 12$	12
4 out of 6	Short essay	$4 \times 7 = 28$	28
1 out of 2	Long essay	$1 \times 10 = 10$	10
Total Semester Marks			50

Pattern of Question Paper in End Semester Examination for Second Semester

The question paper pattern in each Semester Exam for 50 marks consists of Objective type one mark questions 8 questions out of 10 (8 marks), Seven marks questions 4 out of 6 questions (28 marks) , and one long essay of 14 marks out of two (14 marks).

No. of Questions	Type	Marks/Question	Total Marks
8 out of 10	Multiple choice/objective	$8 \times 1 = 8$	8
4 out of 6	Short essay	$4 \times 7 = 28$	28
1 out of 2	Long essay	$1 \times 14 = 14$	14
Total Semester Marks			50

Practicals /Lab Papers :

Semester I & II

1. English Language Communication - 50 marks
2. Computer Skills – 50 marks
3. Field Practicum/ NGO Internship – 100 marks
4. Seminar and Group Presentation – 50 marks

Semester III

1. Summer Placemen/Industry internship – 100 marks
2. Field Practicum – 100 marks
3. Seminar and Group Presentation – 50 marks

Semester IV

1. Field Practicum – 100 marks (50 marks internal + 50 marks external Viva-Voce)
2. Seminar and Group Presentation – 50 marks
3. Research Project – 100 marks(50 marks internal + 50 marks external Viva-Voce)

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College of Social Science and Humanities

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The following members were present for the meeting

1. Dr. Suresh Kumar P.M.
2. Dr. I.C. Licamma
3. Mr. Pradeep M.D.
4. Mrs. Laveena D'Mello
5. Mrs. Indu Nair
6. Dr. Meena Monthiero

During the BOS meeting, the following aspects were discussed and the resolutions were taken.

1. **To plan the syllabus:** The syllabus copy was given in advance to refer and same was discussed. Some changes were done in the syllabus and same was approved.
Resolution: The syllabus was approved by the BOS members.

2. To offer dual specialization subject: In the syllabus the dual specialization subjects were identified, and similar subjects were discussed in the meeting.
Resolution: The dual specialization subjects were approved.
3. **Internship:** Internship was made compulsory and which have 100 marks and done during the vacation after even semester and same will be consider for marks in third semester.
Resolution: The internship and Marks were approved during the meeting.
4. **Field Practicum:** Field practicum credits were discussed and same was approved the marks, hours and the credits were corrected and approved.
Resolution: The Field Practicum pattern was approved in the meeting and credits, Marks and hours of field practicum was finalized.
5. **Study material preparation:** It was discussed as a part of curriculum all teaching staff have to prepare study material as per syllabus. So the study material was shared with the students. The study material include the syllabus, teaching plan, material, and question bank and model question paper.
Resolution: It is made compulsory to prepare study material and to supply the students before examination.
6. **Academic calendar and exams:** Academic calendar was presented and discussed in the meeting
Resolution: Calendar, internship duration and vacation was approved.
7. **Internal assessment:** Internal assessment pattern was discussed with 50 internal marks and 50 external marks. Same was discussed and approved
Resolution: Internal marks division with two internal exams marks and assignment marks were divided to assess the ongoing student's assessment.
8. **Attendance:** Attendance for the students it is made mandatory for allowing them to write examination.
Resolution: 75% attendance is compulsory to appear for exam.
9. **SAAS:** To use the system to mark attendance, for examination, to add internal marks and also lesson plans.
Resolution: It was made mandatory to follow the system and to update the attendance every day.
10. **Question paper patters:** The question paper pattern was changed and same was discussed in the meeting. And it is approved.
Resolution: the new question paper pattern was approved.
11. **Internal and External Paper setters:** The list of the internal and external examiners were approved.

Resolution: New list of examiner was produced and same was approved in the meeting.

Resolution: New examiners and BOE members list was approved.

12. **Project and team projects:** It is compulsory for the students to submit the project and also opportunity for the students to do team project option is given in the syllabus and same as been approved. They were asked to present at least one research paper before completing the course.

Resolution: Project was approved and also opportunity to have team project for the students.

During the meeting many issues related to new syllabus and credit system and the days for field work etc was discussed in detail. Students were asked to submit their field practicum report in typed form. Internship was made compulsory for the students. Dual specialization was introduced and the three specializations were kept for the students like Human resource Development, Medical and Psychiatric and the Community development was the common specialization kept for the students.

The meeting was ended at 5.00 pm with formal vote of thanks by the chair person.

Date: 26/06/2017

Place: Mangalore

Dean

Srinivas University

Department of Social Work

M.S.W. Programme

Board of Studies (BOS) – 2017-18

Sl. No.	Name	Designation	Qualification	Status
1 .	Dr. Suresh Kumar P.M.	Professor	M.S.W., M.Phil., Ph.D. 15 years teaching experience	Chairman
2.	Dr. I. C. Licamma	Professor	M.S.W., Ph.D. 25 years teaching	Member
3.	Mr. Pradeep M.D.	Assistant Professor	M.S.W., M.A., L.L.B., L.L.M., PGDM (Ph.D. doing) 10 years teaching experience	Member
4.	Mrs. Laveena D'Mello	Assistant Professor	M.S.W. (Ph.D. submitted) 15 years teaching experience	Member
5.	Mrs. Indu Nair	-	M.S.W., UGC JRF SLET passed	Member
6.	Dr. Meena Monthiero	--	M.S.W., Ph.D. 19 years teaching experience	Member

Dean